

FROM SCREENS TO STRAIN: A STUDY OF MULTISCREEN ADDICTION, DOOMSCROLLING, AND DIGITAL BURNOUT IN YOUNG ADULTS

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to explore the relationship between multiscreen addiction, doomsScrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. The study hypothesized that multiscreen addiction, doomsScrolling, and digital burnout would be positively associated in young adults. It was also proposed that multiscreen addiction and doomsScrolling would be the positive predictors of digital burnout in young adults. Meanwhile, the study also postulated that there would be meaningful gender differences in correspondence to study variables. In the current study, 201 participants comprising 68 men and 133 women were approached by taking into account the inclusion criteria of the study, such as active social media users aged between 18 to 30 years. Quantitative research was carried out by using a cross-sectional research design, and a purposive sampling technique was used. To examine the sample, the self-constructed demographic sheet, Multiple Screen Addiction Scale (Saritepeci, 2021), DoomsScrolling Scale (Sharma et al., 2022), and the Digital Burnout Scale (Erten & Ozdemir, 2020) were used. The results showed significant positive associations between multiscreen addiction, doomsScrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. Further, it was found that multiscreen addiction and doomsScrolling were positively predicted by digital burnout in young adults. In addition, the results also indicated no significant gender difference in all the study variables. Therefore, the results of the study substantially contributed to cyberpsychology by examining how multiscreen usage and doomsScrolling played a role in the development of digital burnout in young adults.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern era of digitalization, technology is ubiquitous, and everyone has equal access to it. Anyone can use it anywhere for ample of purposes, such as for educational and professional applications, for entertainment and leisure activities. This widespread engagement of technology in fast-

paced daily life not only brings convenience and efficiency but also contributes to the novel challenges in the technologically mediated societies. The versatile applications of technology and its continuous usage potentially promote the elevated level of technologically induced stress, anxiety, and

screen addiction in young adults (Aragay et al., 2023). Advancements in technology, while offering a plethora of benefits, have also contributed to a range of psychological effects, and multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout are the contemporary psychological concerns of the modern era (Litan, 2025). The young adults are especially susceptible to these constructs due to the sheer amount of time they spend using technology to study, work, and also to entertain themselves. Among them, multiscreen addiction can be regarded as the most serious, which is characterized by inappropriate overuse of multiple screens in everyday tasks (Gokalp, 2022). Multiscreen addiction also refers to the overuse and compulsive use of more than one screen, such as television, mobile phones, tablets, and laptops, etc. which negatively impacts health, social abilities, and academic performance (Kader & Fatima, 2024). According to Shahzad et al. (2022), it was found that smartphones as the most widely used screen device among youngsters. In addition, prolonged usage of various screens leads to other phenomena such as doomscrolling, which is characterized by an obsessive tendency to constantly read distressing or negative news on social media and internet platforms, even though it can exacerbate worry, tension, and feelings of hopelessness (Singh & Narula, 2024). Doomscrolling is the persistent consumption of distressing, unpleasant, and negative news feeds driven by algorithmic amplification on digital platforms. This behavior is prevalent during times of uncertainty or catastrophe, such as earthquakes, when individuals prioritize staying updated regarding the catastrophic events but unintentionally expose themselves to overwhelming information, which in turn leads to heightened worry, emotional turmoil, and poor mental well-being (George et al., 2024). It also refers to the feeling of powerlessness over the personal addiction to negative news, regardless of awareness of the consequences it has on mental health (Sharme et al., 2022). It is therefore suggested that doomscrolling can develop a vicious loop, in which progressively greater exposure to bad news can increase anxiety and feelings of powerlessness. Consequently, people can struggle to quit despite being aware of the emotional implications it has on their mental health (Gume, 2024). Both of these behaviors are

contributing factors to digital burnout, a mental state marked by restlessness, cognitive problems, emotional fatigue, and increased anxiety or stress levels resulting from excessive use of technology (Goldag, 2022). Digital burnout also refers to a persistent condition of stress and fatigue resulting from prolonged use of digital gadgets, online work, and social media interactions (Erten & Ozdemir, 2020). It is harmful to mental health as it intensifies the levels of experiencing exhaustion, anxiety, and emotional overload due to an ongoing level of digital engagement and information saturation. Long-term screen time and the inability to dissociate with the technological object (be it career or technology) are linked to higher degrees of anxiety, irritability, and feelings of helplessness. Furthermore, co-occurring physical symptoms like fatigue and sleep disorders can intensify psychiatric issues and thus form a self-perpetuating loop that deteriorates emotional health and the overall quality of life (Nardin et al., 2025). With respect to the theoretical foundation, the examined variables of the current study can be best explained with the help of the uses and gratification theory given by Katz et al. (1973). According to this theory, individuals actively use various forms of media to fulfill their social and psychological needs. This theory emphasizes that individuals seek media to fulfill their need for information, enjoyment, escapism, and even interaction with others via social media platforms. So, when young adults intentionally and frequently engage in multiscreen usage to satisfy these needs, the algorithmic reinforcement and the persistent pursuit of unsatisfactory gratifications strengthen these behaviors, and ultimately, individuals suffer from digital burnout- a mental state marked by emotional exhaustion, cognitive overload, and digital fatigue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various international and indigenous studies have been conducted that highlighted the relationships between study variables. In a study conducted by Gregerson et al. (2023) in Denmark aimed at examining the association between online fatigue and digital dependence during the COVID-19 period. They concluded the positive relationship and highlighted that relying on digital devices led to online exhaustion and fatigue-related emotions.

Furthermore, Saidah et al. (2025) concluded that doomscrolling was positively associated with heightened anxiety, disrupted sleep, and poor concentration, driven by FOMO (fear of missing out), curiosity, and the need for social connectivity. Parallel findings revealed the positive association between doomscrolling and increased screen time with depression, anxiety, and stress (Satici et al., 2024; Niazi et al., 2022). Kader and Fatima (2024) undertook a study aimed at examining the extent of multiscreen addiction among school students and concluded that the majority of participants exhibited a moderate multiscreen addiction level, and a few had an above-average or below-average multiscreen addiction. Priya et al. (2024) concluded that a substantial proportion of respondents experienced adverse mental health effects due to the increased screen time during the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, a study conducted by Ali et al. (2020) concluded that participants exhibited high levels of multiscreen addiction, which in turn contributes to poor sleep quality and low self-control. Ahmed (2022) revealed in a study that individuals who have higher screen time exhibited elevated psychological distress, and in terms of gender difference, male participants showed greater dependence than female participants. During the COVID-19 lockdown, increased usage of multiscreen was associated with digital fatigue, irrespective of age (Wahid et al., 2022). Usman et al. (2025) investigated the correlation between doomscrolling and the mental health of media studies students in Karachi and revealed that there was a strong positive relationship between doomscrolling and poor mental well-being. The study highlighted that those who engaged in more than two hours of doomscrolling were more likely to experience psychological distress.

Rationale of the Study

The internet and multiple displays are utilized for both professional dealings and personal enjoyment. Across the globe, in February 2025, 5.56 billion people used the internet for versatile applications, and among them, 5.24 billion were solely utilizing the internet for social media (Petrosyan, 2025). In January 2025, the number of internet users in Pakistan reached 116 million, and this represents a

significant rise in users, relatively to January 2024, which was 1.7 million (DataReportal, 2025). These statistics vividly indicate the usage of the internet at the national and global level, with the rapid advancement of technology. Although the internet provides a lot of benefits to users but it has potential dangers. The young population is more vulnerable to experiencing technologically induced stress, anxiety, and screen addiction due to their constant engagement and limitless access to screens. Saat et al. (2024) concluded that constant engagement with digital gadgets is associated with heightened anxiety, sleep impairment, and symptoms of depression. Furthermore, most of the studies in correspond to examined study variables have been conducted in Western countries and not in Pakistan, where digital literacy and mental health resources are limited. Thus, by taking into account it is essential to explore the interrelation of multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout among young adults to inform mental health and digital wellness initiatives in Pakistan.

Objectives of the Study

There are three primary objectives of the current study, which are stated below:

To study the association between multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout among active users of social media.

- To analyze the predictive role of multiscreen addiction and doomscrolling for digital burnout.
- To investigate differences between genders with respect to the examined study variables.

Hypotheses of the Study

H1: Multiscreen Addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout are likely to be positively associated in young adults.

H2: Multiscreen Addiction and doomscrolling are likely to be positive predictors of digital burnout in young adults.

H3: Multiscreen Addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout are expected to differ significantly across genders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The cross-sectional research design was employed in the present study to investigate the association between multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout among young adults.

Sample and Sampling Strategy

The Participants (N=201) were active social media users, aged 18 to 30 years (M = 21.45, SD = 2.25), and were taken from four public and private sector universities of Lahore. The participants were recruited using the purposive sampling strategy. The demographics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (N=201)

Variables	f (%)	M(SD)
Age (years)	-	21.45(2.25)
Gender		
Male	68(33.8)	-
Female	133(66.2)	-
Education	-	14.73(1.55)
University		
Public Sector	100(49.8)	-
Private Sector	101(50.2)	-
Marital Status		
Single	13(6.5)	-
Committed	21(10)	-
Married	168(83.6)	-
Family System		
Nuclear Family	121(60.2)	-
Extended Family	79(39.3)	-
Family Monthly Income		133684.21(152269.52)
Any Physical issues		
Yes	191(95)	-
No	10(5)	-
Any Psychological Issue		
Yes	188(93.5)	-
No	13(6.5)	-
Frequently used Screen		
Smartphone	178(88.6)	
Laptop/Desktop	13(6.5)	
Tablet	3(1.5)	
Smartphone	3(1.5)	
Multiscreening		
Yes	93(46.3)	
No	108(53.7)	
Total Screen Time (Daily)		26.58(14.72)
With Internet		5.93(4.99)
Without Internet		2.58(4.19)

Assessment Measures

Four assessment measures were used in the current study, which are stated below:

Demographic Information Sheet

In this study, researchers developed a demographic information sheet. Questions included in this sheet related to age, gender, education level, marital status, residential area, family monthly income, family system, and information related to multiscreen usage.

Multiple Screen Addiction Scale (Santepeci, 2021)

This scale was used to measure behaviors related to addiction across multiple digital devices, like smartphones, tablets, and computers. The scale comprises 15 items across three domains, which are compulsive behavior, loss of control, and excessive screen time. These subscales are designed to assess various forms of digital addiction. The items of the scale are rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = *Never*, 2 = *Rarely*, 3 = *Sometimes*, 4 = *Often*, and 5 = *Always*). The increased ratings are an indicator of increased severity of multi-screen addiction. The reliability of the overall multiscreen addiction scale is reported as .92, while its sub-dimensions indicated the alpha reliability ranged from .71 to .92 (Santepeci, 2021).

Doomscrolling Scale (Sharma et al., 2022)

This scale was used to measure the individual's tendency to engage in continuous consumption of negative news, particularly on social media platforms. It is a unidimensional scale and has 15 items. All items of the scale are rated on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree*, 2 = *disagree*, 3 = *somewhat disagree*, 4 = *neutral*, 5 = *somewhat agree*, 6 = *agree*, and 7 = *strongly agree*). The higher the scores, the more engagement in doomscrolling behavior on the internet. The reliability of the doomscrolling scale is reported as .96 (Sharma et al., 2022).

Digital Burnout (Erten & Ozdemir, 2020)

This scale was utilized to measure varying degrees of digital burnout in young adults. The scale is composed of 24 items and is divided into three sub-dimensions, which are digital aging, digital deprivation, and emotional exhaustion. The items of the scale are rated on a five-point Likert scale from 1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*. The higher score indicates higher digital burnout. The reliability of the overall digital burnout scale is 0.95, and its sub-dimensions, such as digital aging 0.92, digital

deprivation 0.88, and emotional exhaustion 0.86 (Erten & Ozdemir, 2020).

Procedure

For the current study, permissions were obtained from the authors to use their scales, and they allowed us to do so. Data were collected from different university students, and at first, consent forms were filled out by the participants, and they were provided with a brief description of the study. They were also informed about their right to withdraw from the study without any penalty if they felt uneasy or did not want to proceed. The research was anonymous, and participants were encouraged to respond honestly. Almost 10-15 minutes were taken by each respondent to complete the data collection form. For the present study, 230 were approached, and 201 were selected, and the rest were excluded because of the incomplete or zigzag responses. The response rate was reported as 87.40%. After the data collection, the results were analyzed in SPSS.

Ethical Considerations

All ethical guidelines outlined by the American Psychological Association (APA, 2017) were strictly followed in this study. Data collection was done by approaching the participants who met the inclusion criteria of the research. For data collection from the participants of the respective universities, permission was obtained from the respective universities. Before filling out the questionnaire, the consent form was taken from each participant. The participants had been briefed about the nature of the study. They were informed that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential. They had the right to withdraw from the study at any time. Results were reported accurately.

RESULTS

After the data had been collected and entered into the software, initial screening was conducted to deal with potential outliers and missing values. All results were analyzed using SPSS-26 version.

Table 2: Psychometric Properties of the Scales and Subscales (N=201)

Scales	K	M(SD)	Range	Cronbach's α
Multiscreen Addiction Scale	15	43(9.64)	17-78	.79
Excessive Screen Time	4	11(3.03)	4-20	.60
Compulsive Behavior	8	23(6.28)	9-60	.70
Loss of Control	3	8(2.43)	3-14	.51
Doomscrolling Scale	15	41(15.17)	14-84	.87
Digital Burnout Scale	24	71(15.62)	34-111	.87
Digital Aging	12	36(8.99)	14-69	.78
Digital Deprivation	6	17(4.78)	6-30	.76
Emotional Exhaustion	6	17(4.61)	7-30	.76

Note. M = mean, SD = Standard deviation, k = no. of items

Table 2 showed descriptive statistics (Mean, Standard deviation, range) and Cronbach's alphas of the scales used in the present study. The results showed the multiscreen addiction scale reported .79 reliability, and its subscales ranged between .51 to .70. The

doomscrolling scale indicated .87 reliability. The digital burnout scale reported .87 reliability, and its subscales reported .76 to .78 reliability. Hence, the reliability of the measurement scales was good enough to carry out further analyses.

Table 3: Correlations for Variables of Study (N=201)

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Multiscreen Addiction	-	.73*	.92*	.68*	.23**	.53**	.46**	.45**	.43**
2. Excessive Screen Time		-	.48*	.42*	.13	.36**	.35**	.26**	.27**
3. Compulsive Behavior			-	.46*	.17*	.46**	.38**	.43**	.37**
4. Loss of Control				-	.29**	.43**	.37**	.34**	.36**
5. Doomscrolling					-	.41**	.34**	.77**	.81**
6. Digital Burnout						-	.92**	.77**	.81**
7. Digital Aging							-	.54**	.58**
8. Digital Deprivation								-	.56**
9. Emotional Exhaustion									-

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

The results of Table 3 indicated that multiscreen addiction was positively related to doomscrolling and digital burnout in young adults. Meanwhile, a positive correlation exists between doomscrolling and digital burnout in young adults. Furthermore, Multiscreen addiction is positively related to subscales of digital burnout, which are digital aging, digital deprivation, and emotional exhaustion. In addition,

subscales of multiscreen addiction were positively related to doomscrolling and digital burnout. The subscales of multiscreen addiction, such as excessive screen time, compulsive behavior, and loss of control, were positively related to subscales of digital burnout, i.e., digital aging, digital deprivation, and emotional exhaustion.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients Predicting Digital Burnout among Young Adults (N=201)

Predictors	B	SE	β	95% of CI
Constant	27.18***	4.37		[18.56, 35.83]
Multiscreen Addiction	.74**	.095	.45**	[.56, .93]
Doomscrolling	.31**	.06	.29**	[.18, .42]
R ²	.357			
F (2, 198)	55.03***			

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

The results of Table 4 show that the model's overall variance is 35.7%, with $F(2, 198) = 55.03, p < .001$. The results showed that multiscreen addiction ($\beta = .45, p < .001$) and doomscrolling ($\beta = .29, p < .001$) were identified as positive predictors of digital burnout in young adults.

The same analysis was performed on the subscales of multiscreen addiction and doomscrolling to determine the predictors of digital burnout among young adults (see Table 5).

Table 5: Regression Coefficients of Subscales Predicting Digital Burnout among Young Adults (N=201)

Predictors	B	SE	β	95% of CI
Constant	27.36***	4.48		[18.53, 36.21]
Excessive Screen Time	.62	3.48	.12	[-.06, 1.31]
Compulsive Behavior	.69**	.17	.28**	[.36, 1.04]
Loss of Control	1.05**	.44	.16**	[.18, 1.92]
Doomscrolling	.29**	.06		[.17, .42]
R ²	.359			
F (4, 196)	27.45***			

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

The results of Table 5 show that the model's overall variance is 35.9%, with $F(4, 196) = 27.45, p < .001$. The results showed that doomscrolling ($\beta = .28, p < .001$) and two subscales of multiscreen addiction, such as compulsive behavior ($\beta = .28, p < .001$) and

loss of control ($\beta = .16, p < .05$) were found to be the positive predictors of digital burnout in young adults. However, the excessive screen time subscale of multiscreen addiction was not found to be a predictor of digital burnout in young adults.

Table 6: Gender Difference in Study Variables (N=201)

Variables	Men n = 68		Women n = 133		t (199)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Multiscreen Addiction	44.08	10.23	42.86	9.34	.86	.95	-
Excessive Screen Time	12.08	3.05	11.59	3.02	1.08	.95	-
Compulsive Behavior	23.74	7.27	23.38	5.74	.37	.77	-
Loss of Control	8.26	2.64	7.87	2.31	1.06	.20	-
Doomscrolling	41.57	15.85	41.22	14.88	.16	.38	-
Digital Burnout	71.18	16.31	72.06	15.33	-.37	.65	-
Digital Aging	35.55	9.09	36.29	8.96	-.56	.65	-

Digital Deprivation	18.08	4.74	17.57	4.82	.72	.73	-
Emotional Exhaustion	17.55	5.27	18.19	4.22	-.94	.08	-

The findings showed that multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout showed no significant gender differences in young adults.

DISCUSSION

The primary goal of the present study was to analyze the association between multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. The rapid advancement in technology has altered the way people learn, interact, and communicate with technological gadgets, and particularly young adults are more susceptible to experiencing technologically induced stress, anxiety, and screen addiction due to their excessive engagement and limitless access to technology. In recent years, ample challenges appeared due to the ubiquity of technology, and multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout are the contemporary issues that are prevalent among the young population. By taking into account these changing trends of digital interaction, the current study aims to investigate the interrelation of multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. The findings of the current research study showed that multiscreen addiction is significantly positively correlated with doomscrolling and digital burnout, as well as its sub-dimensions, among young adults. Our findings are also in line with the existing study conducted by Priya et al. (2024), who investigated the connection between the effect of higher screen time and digital behavior on the physical and mental health of young adults during the COVID-19 period. They concluded that higher screen time adversely affected physical and mental health and overall well-being, which is consistent with the present results. In another study, Ahmed (2022) investigated the relationship between screen time addiction and psychological suffering among adults. The results showed that screen time addiction and psychological distress have a strong positive relationship. This study also indicates that higher degrees of screen time addiction correlate with an amplified degree of psychological distress. The results of the present study are in line with that study. Furthermore, the

results of the present study are also aligned with a study conducted by Wahid et al. (2022), which showed a positive association between screen addiction and digital fatigue during the COVID-19 Pandemic. It was also hypothesized that multiscreen addiction and doomscrolling are likely to be positive predictors of digital burnout in young adults. In the present study, to test this hypothesis, a multiple regression analysis was carried out, and the results supported this hypothesis. These findings are consistent with Wahid et al. (2021), who studied screen-time addiction as a predictor of digital fatigue. Their study recruited 180 participants and found that there was a positive relationship between screen-time addiction and digital fatigue in young adults. High screen-time dependency is, in turn, related to increasing degrees of digital fatigue among young adults. The results of this current study also go in line with the study of Saboor et al. (2024). The results of their study concluded that digital workload was positively predicted by digital burnout. In the present study, the reliability and relevance of the results can be strengthened by the uniformity across contexts. In the current study, it was also assumed that there would likely be a significant gender difference. This was testified by an independent sample t-test analysis, and the results are contrary to the hypothesis. The findings of the current study highlighted that there was no difference in gender with respect to multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. These findings are aligned with the study of Wahid et al. (2021), who investigated the interplay of multiscreen addiction and digital fatigue. Their study found no gender difference in multiscreen addiction and digital fatigue. This aligned well with the results of the present study. On the contrary, Ahmed (2022) conducted a study to examine the relationship between screen time addiction and psychological distress in adults. The study results showed significant gender differences, with male participants reporting higher levels of screen time addiction than female participants. Further, another study conducted by Niazi et al. (2022) explored the association between screen time

and depression or anxiety. The results of that study in terms of gender difference indicated that female participants had more depression or anxiety related to screen time as compared to male participants. The disparity in gender differences results in different studies, which might be attributed to a number of factors. For instance, variances in sample demographics, cultural settings, and the changing patterns of digital media usage are fundamental aspects that can lead to disparities in gender differences. In addition, the ubiquity of technology in the modern era led to equal access in rural areas, and hence, anyone, anywhere can access technological gadgets easily. Earlier studies have revealed more prominent gender norms in technology use, but contemporary advancements suggest convergence across gender. Furthermore, discrepancies in construct measurement tools, cut-off criteria for multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout, the size of the sample, and statistical power may explain the disparity in results.

Limitations and Suggestions

The sample was chosen on the basis of a group of young adults who used the internet actively. The subsequent research can utilize various age groups and generations by implementing cross-generational impacts to study the same phenomenon. The present study was quantitative in nature, and future research should employ qualitative research methods to gain deeper insights into the experiences and perceptions of individuals regarding the phenomenon under study. They may also consider including differently-abled individuals to explore how the results might differ across populations with varying physical or cognitive conditions. It is suggested that extending the sample to include participants from other universities beyond Lahore would help increase the generalizability of the findings across different socio-geographic backgrounds. Furthermore, the measurement scales were utilized in this study, developed in Western contexts, which may sometimes lead to inaccurate results when applied in Eastern settings due to huge differences in culture, language, norms, and social experiences. So, measurement scales must be developed on local parameters and demographics for more reliable and accurate results.

Implications of the Study

The findings of the study are an addition to the indigenous research literature exploring the relationship between multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. The findings of the study highlighted an urgent action plan at the university level to minimize digital burnout among students through mental health interventions, counseling, awareness programs, and workshops that provide tangible strategies for screen time management. In addition, the academic institutions should incorporate digital wellness programs into orientation sessions and student support services, as the sample was obtained from young adults of both public and private sector universities in Lahore.

Furthermore, the current study has the potential to substantially contribute to cyberpsychology and digital media studies by highlighting how multiscreen usage and excessive consumption of distressing news contribute to digital burnout in the young population. The study also emphasized promoting media literacy among young adults to help them critically evaluate and manage the emotional impact of doomscrolling during times of crises at the national or global level. Meanwhile, the findings of the current study also hold relevance for public health policy as they vividly indicate how multiscreen usage and consumption of negative news ultimately contribute to digital burnout. The public health experts may address the psychological effects of excessive digital exposure in young adults through digital wellness initiatives at the macro level.

Conclusion

In the current study, the results concluded that there was a positive relationship between multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout in young adults. This clearly shows that individuals who engage more in screens such as mobile phones, laptops, tablets, and computers are at higher risk of engaging in doomscrolling behavior, which in turn ultimately contributes to digital burnout. This pattern is prevalent in low-income countries and particularly in Pakistan due to ample of contributing factors, such as technological factors-social media access to psychological factors, escapism, and cultural factors-peer pressure. Furthermore, the present study

showed that multiscreen addiction and doomscrolling positively predicted digital burnout in young adults. This trend was vividly shown during times of political instability, economic crises, war, earthquakes, floods, and a disease outbreak. In these circumstances, young adults spend time switching devices or doomscrolling and ultimately experience symptoms of digital burnout. Moreover, the results showed that there was no statistically significant gender difference in study variables. In Pakistan, particularly in the province, Lahore, male and female participants showed similar levels of multiscreen addiction, doomscrolling, and digital burnout.

To sum up, the current study indicates how ubiquitous technology in the modern era is creating new psychological issues for young adults. The increasing reliance of young adults on screens, either for education, online video games, or professional activities, is contributing to poor digital behavior, and this is an alarming condition in Pakistan, where already a lot of problems exist, from political instability to fewer resources and a lack of awareness of digital behaviors. Therefore, this study points out that it is a need of the hour to take interventions that target healthier screen-use practices, encourage regulated screen time, and implement tangible strategies to reduce the digital burnout in young adults.

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